

Chromosomal Studies on Three Species of Scarabaeinae Beetles (Polyphaga : Scarabaeidae)

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Ashish Rathore

Research Scholar
Department Of Zoology
P.M. College Of Excellence Govt. P.G. Arts
And Science College
Ratlam,M.P., India ,

B.S. Kirade

Assistant Professor
Department Of Zoology
Govt. P.G. College, Jaora
Ratlam, M.P., India

Milind Dange

Professor
Department Of Zoology
P.M. College of Excellence Govt. P.G. Arts
and Science College
Ratlam, M.P., India

Abstract	Karyological investigations were carried out on adult male individuals of three species of Scarabaeinae beetles viz. <i>Onthophagus bonasus</i> Fabricius, <i>O. carinensis</i> Boucomont and <i>O. nasalis</i> Arrow. All species possesses $2n = 20 : 9 + Xy_p$. Mitosis and meiosis have been described and discussed.
Keywords	Coleoptera, Scarabaeinae, Karyotype, Autosome, Sex Chromosome Mechanism.
Introduction	Scarabaeidae is the largest family of Coleoptera comprising 30,000 species. Its subfamily Scarabaeinae is especially diverse in tropics where they dominate another large group of dung beetles Aphodiinae. Members of this subfamily are commonly called dung beetles. Many species feed on mammalian dung whereas others specialize to varying degrees upon the dung of other vertebrates and invertebrates, as well as on carrion, mushrooms, rotting fruit, and other decomposing plant material. The World fauna includes 7,000 described species in 234 genera, with close to 1,800 of these species belonging to the genus <i>Onthophagus</i> (Halffter and Matthews 1966, Halffter and Edmonds 1982, Hanski and Cambefort 1991, Vaz-de-Mello 2000). Dung beetles play important ecological roles and they are highly sensitive to global climate change. Keeping in view the economic importance and paucity of literature on the chromosomes of this group, the present investigation on the three species were under taken. Cytological details of three species have been given.
Objective of study	To investigate the karyological features (chromosome number and structure) of three species of <i>Onthophagus</i> dung beetles and compare their chromosomal patterns to understand variations and similarities within the Scarabaeinae subfamily.
Review of Literature	Cytogenetic studies on Scarabaeidae beetles have been conducted by various researchers such as Dasgupta (1963), Manna & Lahiri (1972), Virkki (1951–1967), and Yadav & Pillai (1974, 1979), who reported chromosome numbers and sex chromosome mechanisms across several species. Rathore (2010) specifically investigated the karyotypes of some Scarabaeoid beetles and confirmed the prevalence of a modal diploid number ($2n = 20$) with a Xy_p sex-determining system. However, detailed karyomorphological data for many Indian species remain scarce. The present study adds to this body of knowledge by focusing on three lesser-studied species of <i>Onthophagus</i> . Rathore <i>et al.</i> (2025) conducted karyological analysis of four dung beetle species, revealing interspecific differences in chromosome number and morphology, which support their cytotoxic distinctions within Geotrupidae and Scarabaeidae.
Methodology	Adult male individuals of <i>Onthophagus bonasus</i> Fabricius, <i>O. carinensis</i> Boucomont and <i>O. nasalis</i> Arrow. constituted the materials for the present investigations. All the beetles were collected under the mercury vapour lamps during June to September 2024- 2025 from Ratlam (Madhya Pradesh) and Pratapgarh (Rajasthan). Chromosome preparations were made following Yadav and Lyapunova (1983).
Result and Discussion	Onthophagus bonasus Fabricius

The diploid number of 20 chromosomes was revealed by spermatogonial metaphase (Fig. 01). The karyotype is composed of nine pairs of autosomes and X and y sex chromosomes (Fig. 02). Autosome pair 1, 2 and 7 was metacentric, pair 3-6, 8 and 9 were submetacentric and the X and y chromosomes were metacentric. When arranged according to size the autosomes show a gradual decrease. The chromatids appear closely applied to one another throughout their lengths.

Metaphase I posses nine rod shaped autosomal bivalents and the sex bivalent in the form of a parachute (Fig. 07).

The male chromosomal formula is $9AA + Xy_p$.

Onthophagus carinesis Boucomont

Spermatogonial metaphase is characterized by the presence of 20 chromosomes (Fig. 03). The karyotype comprises nine pairs of autosomes and X and y sex chromosomes. Autosome pairs 1, 5, 9 are metacentric and autosome pairs 2-4, 6-8 and X chromosome was submetacentric while y chromosome was smallest and sub- metacentric (Fig. 04).

At metaphase I nine autosomal bivalents and the sex bivalent Xy_p were observed (Fig. 08). The autosomal bivalents are either dumb-bells or rod shaped. As a result of the first meiotic division two types of metaphase II plates were formed one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig. 09).

The male chromosomal formula is $9AA+ Xy_p$.

Onthophagus nasalis Arrow

The diploid number of 20 chromosomes was revealed by spermatogonial metaphase (Fig. 05). The karyotype is composed of nine pairs of autosomes and X and y sex chromosomes (Fig. 06). Autosome pairs 3 and 5 were metacentric, pairs 1, 2, 4-8 along with the X chromosome were submetacentric, while y chromosome was acrocentric. Metaphase I possess nine rods or dumb-bells shaped autosomal bivalents and the sex bivalent Xy_p . (Fig. 10) As a result of the first meiotic division being reductional two types of metaphase II plates are formed one with X chromosome and the other with y chromosome (Fig. 11).

The male chromosomal formula is $9AA+ Xy_p$.

A perusal of the literature on the karyology of Laprostickti (Dasgupta, 1963; Hayden, 1925; Dange, 1991; Joneja, 1960; Kacker, 1970, 1971; Manna & Lahiri, 1972; Rathore, 2010; Smith, 1953; Virkki, 1951, 1954, 1959, 1967 and Yadav & Pillai, 1974, 1979) reveals the cytological data of 144 species, of these 102 possesses the modal number. All the species under present investigations also possess the modal karyotype. During the course of present investigations the total chromosome length was found to be maximum in *O. carinensis* Boucomont (59.90μ) and minimum in *O. bonasus* Fabricius (44.55μ). All chromosomes show a gradual decrease in size. The size of X chromosome was smallest in *O. bonasus* Fabricius (1.86μ) and largest in *O. carinensis* Boucomont (2.61μ). *O. carinensis* Boucomont has the largest y (2.21μ) whereas y was smallest in *O. bonasus* Fabricius (1.78μ).

Comparative study of the karyotypes of the beetles is presented in table 1.

Table 1: Karyotype analysis of three species of *Onthophagus* spp.

Sr. No.	Species	Chromosome pairs in percentage length											Length in μ		
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	X	Y	TCL	X	Y
1	<i>Onthophagus bonasus</i> Fabricius	13.00	10.70	10.00	9.83	9.70	9.70	9.05	9.02	7.50	3.72	3.56	44.55	1.86	1.78
2	<i>O. carinensis</i> Boucomont	16.10	14.00	14.00	13.60	13.00	12.90	12.90	12.20	11.10	5.30	4.41	59.90	2.65	2.21
3	<i>O. nasalis</i> Arrow	17.50	14.05	12.40	11.68	11.80	10.53	10.34	10.28	8.68	3.08	3.97	53.76	1.99	1.90

TCL = Total chromosome length.

Fig.1 Spermatogonial metaphase of *Onthophagus bonasus* Fabricius
Fig.2 Karyotype of the same
Fig.3 Spermatogonial metaphase of *O. carinensis* Boucomont
Fig.4 Karyotype of the same
Fig.5 Spermatogonial metaphase of *O. nasalis* Arrow
Fig.6 Karyotype of the same
Fig.7 *Onthophagus bonasus* Fabricius (Metaphase I)
Fig.8 *O. carinensis* Boucomont (Metaphase I)
Fig.9 *O. carinensis* Boucomont (Metaphase II)
Fig.10 *O. nasalis* Arrow (Metaphase I)

Fig.11 *O. nasalis* Arrow (Metaphase II)

Conclusion

All three Onthophagus species studied have a diploid number of $2n = 20$ and share the Xy_p sex-determination system. While their overall karyotype structure is similar, species-specific differences exist in chromosome morphology and size, especially in sex chromosomes. These findings support the conserved nature of Scarabaeinae karyotypes and add valuable data to beetle cytogenetics.

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